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STUDY OF COMPLEX RESISTANCE OF SELENIUM RECTIFIERS

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ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ КОМПЛЕКСНОГО СОПРОТИВЛЕНИЯ СЕЛЕНИЕВЫХ ВЫПРЯМИТЕЛЕЙ

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Abstract

Selenium has good photovoltaic and photoconductive properties, and it is widely used in electronics such as photocells, photometers, and solar cells. The second largest use of selenium is in the glass industry: selenium is used to remove color from glass, and to give a red color to glasses and enamels. Selenium can also be used in photocopying and toning of photographs. Its artistic use is to enhance and expand the tonal range of black and white photographic images. Other uses of selenium are in metal alloys such as lead plates used in battery cells and rectifiers to convert AC current to DC current. Selenium is used to increase wear resistance in vulcanized rubbers. Some selenium compounds are added to anti-dandruff shampoos.

The presence and nature of the n semiconductor in selenium rectifiers was judged by the element's thermal and electrical properties. Selenium rectifiers are made of aluminum or steel plates coated with bismuth or nickel about 1 μm .

Researching the thermal conductivity of selenium, the effect of various additives on it, and its changes depending on its crystal structure are of both scientific and practical importance.

Аннотация

Селен обладает хорошими фотоэлектрическими и фотопроводящими свойствами и широко используется в электронике, такой как фотоэлементы, фотометры и солнечные элементы. Второе место по объему использования селена занимает стекольная промышленность: селен используется для обесцвечивания стекла и придания красного цвета стеклу и эмали. Селен также можно использовать при фотокопировании и тонировании фотографий. Его художественное применение заключается в усилении и расширении тонногового диапазона черно-белых фотографических изображений.

Селен также используется в металлических сплавах, таких как свинцовые пластины, используемые в аккумуляторных элементах и выпрямителях для преобразования переменного тока в постоянный. Селен используется для повышения износостойкости вулканизированных каучуков. Некоторые соединения селена добавляются в шампуни против перхоти.

О наличии и природе n-полупроводника в селеновых выпрямителях судили по термическим и электрическим свойствам элемента. Селеновые выпрямители изготавливаются из алюминиевых или стальных пластин, покрытых висмутом или никелем толщиной около 1 мкм.

Исследование теплопроводности селена, влияния на него различных добавок и ее изменения в зависимости от кристаллической структуры имеют как научное, так и практическое значение.

Keywords: crystal, additive, electrode, dielectric, binding layer.

Ключевые слова: кристалл, добавка, электрод, диэлектрик, связующий слой.

1. *Measuring the thickness of the bonding layer.* In planar semiconductor devices, the bonding layer is treated as a dielectric between two electrodes. This dielectric is bounded by a metal on one side and a semiconductor on the other. Therefore, the thickness of the connecting layer is determined according to the capacitance formula of the planar capacitor.

$$\lambda = \frac{\varepsilon S}{4\pi C}$$

where ε is the dielectric constant of the connecting layer substance, S is its area, C is the capacitance.

artificial n-layer selenium rectifiers made it possible to measure the thickness of the bonding layer

by other methods. In this case, it is possible to measure by weight or optically λ .

To determine by weight, λ you need to know the weight of the element before and after n layers are laid. An interference microscope is used to optically determine the thickness of the bonding layer. For this purpose, apart from the electronic semiconductor substrate, it is drawn on the glass plate placed next to it.

In the calculations, the specific gravity of CdS and $CdSe$ is 5.6 and 4.8, and the dielectric constant of both substances is 6.5. The measurement of the thickness of the binding layer according to the capacity $t = +20^\circ C, U = 15mv, U = 0, f = 2000hc$ was carried out in . The value of the thickness of the bonding layer is very close to the capacity and (λ_c), weight (λ_B), measured by the optical method (λ_o)

Small differences in the values of the dimension were observed, which is natural, because λ_o - average values from three dimensions; dielectric constant and field value are measured with certain error. Synergistic optimization of optical and electrical properties of Cu_2Te thin films by doping method with different content of selenium was presented. Selenium layers were successfully deposited by electron beam evaporation on silicon and glass substrates without the formation of non-stoichiometric phases.

During the electrical and thermal forming of the selenium layers $CdS, CdSe$ the layer is improved and thickened. A certain degree of study of this issue shows that the electrical and thermal shaping of selenium rectifiers have the same essence. For this purpose, $U=0, U=15mv, t = +20^\circ C$, before and after forming, the sums of the equivalent circuit in the bridge were determined. The thickness of the binding layer was calculated according to the value of the capacity [2].

Experimental results show that as a result of electric and thermal molding, along with the reduction of direct and reverse current in the plant elements, the capacity decreases, as a result, the layer becomes thicker.

As a result of molding, the resistance of the binding layer increases. As a result of molding, the thickness of n layer increases twice, and R increases ten times. This is explained by the fact that the thin parts of the n layers in the mold become thicker, the current and thus the temperature in those places reach a large value and equalize the layer.

Covering λ individual places under the upper electrode CdS with or increases $CdSe$ the resistance (R) more sharply than the effective thickness.

Selenium has good photovoltaic and photoconductive properties, and it is widely used in electronics such as photocells, photometers, and solar cells. By applying different voltages to the element of selenium and studying its capacity, it is possible to calculate the thickness of the binding layer and the concentration of additional centers there.

Based on the diffusion theory, it is possible to determine the effective density of additive centers in the binding layer. If n is a constant quantity $\frac{1}{C^2}$, that

is, λ^2 the dependence of U on Cartesian coordinates should give a straight line. This means that the layer should monotonically thicken as the stress increases in the bonding direction.

The diffusion theory related to the metal-semiconductor contact can also be applied to selenium rectifiers with some approximation [2]. In the pn contact, the region of both positive (electron semiconductor) and negative (selenium) charges expands in the connecting direction.

The value found for the concentration of additive centers becomes the effective value for the binding layer. As it is clear, let us denote λ_- the thickness of the bonding layer at zero, positive and negative values of the voltage, respectively $\lambda_0, \lambda_+, \lambda_0$. n is the sum of the thickness of the contact bonding layer with the semiconductor. In the experimental error, $\lambda_0 n$ indicates the thickness of the semiconductor, that is, in selenium elements, the bonding layer is so thin compared to the chemical bonding layer that it cannot be measured in the experiment.

the relationship was correct for all samples measured. $\lambda_- > \lambda_0 > \lambda_+$ If we evaluate the property of the rectifier element according to the dependence of the capacity on the voltage, it can be said that the more sharply the capacity changes when the direction of the voltage changes, the better the rectifier will give. This is explained by the fact that the growth limit of the positive and negative parts of the static voltamper characteristic λ_+ is determined by the values of and λ_-

It is very important that the value of λ_+ is small in the straight direction and at small voltages. λ_+ Because the point where the voltmeter characteristic intersects the U axis and the continuation of its linear part will be close to the coordinate origin. The value of this part indicates the potential drop in the rectifier at the nominal current [5].

The thicker the binder, the better. λ Because in this case the reverse characteristic bends at higher voltages.

Thus, the rectification effect of selenium rectifiers is determined by the value of the change in the thickness of the binding layer in a changing electric field. Maximum shrinkage in the straight direction and expansion in the opposite direction are the main factors of straightening.

At a voltage of $\lambda_0 10 V$, it is 4-5 times larger than This means that the main role in closing the current is played by the physical binding layer created by the effect of the external electric field applied in the opposite direction.

The binding layer of selenium elements is "elastic" under the influence of an external field. The degree of elasticity is quantified for different elements at the same stress. λ_- / λ_+ . The larger the ratio, the better the alignment. λ_- determines the high voltage of the rectifier, λ_+ and is the voltage drop in the direct direction. λ_0 a larger straightener is less flexible. Usually, at the rated current ($50 \text{ ma} / \text{cm}^2$), rectifiers with such a barrier layer have a large resistance in the direct direction.

$\lambda_+ < \lambda_0$ the fact that there is shows that the thickness of the part of *n* semiconductor with high resistance decreases at positive values of the voltage. It is determined by the resistance in the straight direction at a given voltage. $\lambda_0 - \lambda_+$. The difference is that the resistance in the straight direction decreases sharply.

In the straight direction, the space charge region disappears in the volume of *the n* semiconductor and in the layer of the *p* semiconductor close to the contact, and the resistance is mainly determined by the thickness of the selenium, which obeys Ohm's law at small voltages.

the *n* semiconductor is thick (10^{-4} cm) even at a voltage of 2-3 V, λ_+ it takes a large value. The remaining $\lambda_- - \lambda_+$ thick layer behaves as a series-connected poor conductor material. Such samples have a very large reverse resistance. In selenium rectifiers, *n* is the optimum thickness corresponding to the maximum value of the rectification coefficient of the semiconductor $5 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ sm}$. In this case, the binding layer is active, when a voltage of 0.50-0.60 is applied in the straight direction, the binding layer disappears. At a reverse voltage of 10-12 V, the thickness of the binding layer increases several times.

The reason for the correction is the sharp change of the specific resistance and thickness of the bonding layer depending on the value of the applied voltage. In selenium rectifiers, the maximum flexibility of the connecting layer is obtained when *pn* contacts are formed. Artificial layers made of quartz, synthetic rubber sulfur, varnish and other insulating material do not have good elastic properties and therefore give poor alignment.

2. Dependence of capacity on temperature

Heat capacities are relatively easy to measure as a function of temperature. Heat capacity is a smooth, continuous function of temperature, except for a small number of discontinuities. These occur at temperatures where matter undergoes phase changes.

These can be a change from one solid phase to another, melting to change a solid phase to a liquid, or evaporation to change a liquid to a gas. We can show such an empirical example:

The heat capacity values suggest an enhancement of the overall structural order in aqueous sugar solutions, i.e., due to the competitive gain of hydrophilic interactions over it. Hydrophobic ones cause an increase in hydrogen bonds. In the case of

ionic solutions, the negative excess heat capacity was attributed to the breaking of hydrogen bonds. Thus, water in aqueous solutions is called electrostriction due to the influence of dissolved molecules.

Among the sugars in this study, fructose had the strongest deviation at higher temperatures and concentrations.

Heat capacities of binary aqueous solutions of different concentrations of sucrose, glucose, fructose, citric acid, malic acid and inorganic salts were measured with a differential scanning calorimeter at temperatures from 5°C to 65°C. Heat capacity increases with increasing amount of water and increasing temperature. At low concentrations, the heat capacity approached that of pure water with a less noticeable effect of temperature and a minimum of 30°C - 40°C. Literature data, when available, agree relatively well with experimental values.

A correction factor based on the assumption of chemical equilibrium between the liquid and gas phase in the Differential Scanning Calorimeter was proposed to correct for water evaporation due to temperature increase. Experimental data were fitted to predictive models. The excess molar heat capacity was calculated using the Redlich-Kister equation to represent the deviation from the additive ideal model.

It can also be explained that the effect of temperature on excess heat capacity is explained by it, as the temperature rises, the bound water decreases. Furthermore, since the interaction is not considered in the ideal additive model, the magnitude of the solute-solvent interaction is larger than that of bulk water at higher temperatures. Aqueous sugar solutions showed a linear dependence on temperature, while citric and malic acids and aqueous salt solutions showed a quadratic dependence on temperature with excess heat.

It can be understood that the absence of a factor complicating the analysis of the excess function indicates the heat capacities of pure compounds as a function of temperature.

At zero, positive and small negative values of the voltage, the capacity of the rectifier decreases as the temperature decreases. At reverse voltages greater than 4-5 v and in the temperature interval - 60 °, +60 ° the capacity does not depend on the temperature experimentally. Such dependence was obtained in 20 samples. In all cases, these dependencies are consistent for artificial stratified and technical samples.

It was shown above that as the displacement in the opposite direction increases, the capacitance decreases and increases in the straight direction. As a result, as the absolute value of the capacitance drops, its temperature dependence becomes sharper.

This shows that the capacitance is mainly due to the variation of layer thickness in *the pn* junction. As a result of the increase in the resistance of the selenium layer at low temperatures, its capacity increases; since this capacitance is connected in series with the capacitance of the bonding layer, its increase reduces the capacitance of the element.

However, as a result of the increase of the Debye radius at the boundary of the semiconductors, the

reduction of the contact layer capacitance plays a key role in the reduction of the element's capacity.

When a certain amount of tension is applied in the straight direction, the area of volume loads narrows; in this case, a reserve layer is created for the temperature-dependent expansion of the physical bonding layer in the *n semiconductor*. A reserve layer is created for such an opportunity expansion. Such a possibility sharpens the capacity dependence.

of a conventional rectifier element and an artificial layered element at different voltages and at a frequency of 2 kHz is given in Figure 1 [6].

The thermodynamic properties of the saturated vapor pressure can indicate the possibility of separation of Se and impurities, while the

kinetic factors of the evaporation rate play a major role in determining the purification efficiency of vacuum distillation.

(Typical sample ϕ 25 mm)

Figure 1 . Selenium at different displacement stresses temperature dependence of the capacity of its elements

It can be seen from the curves that when the value of the voltage is small in the opposite direction and large in the straight direction, the capacity depends

more sharply on the temperature. Under certain temperature and pressure conditions, there is a dynamic

equilibrium between the gas and condensed phases, and the number of molecules that are mutually converted from the condensed and gaseous states per unit of time is equal.

During vacuum distillation of crude selenium, Se molecules break off from the evaporating surface and enter the gas space, forming a metal vapor stream that diffuses in the vapor phase and migrates to the condenser. At a relatively large reverse voltage, the physical bonding layer in the *n*- semiconductor reaches its limiting value, that is, the upper electrode, so the thickness and capacitance are independent of temperature.

Selenium forms several allotropes that interconvert with temperature, depending somewhat on the rate of temperature change. It is denoted by R , which corresponds to the ohmic resistance of the connecting layer. The low-frequency reverse current is mainly determined by this resistance. R strongly depends on the value and direction of the field.

To determine R , the method of determining the parameters of the equivalent circuit is used, adding a small alternating voltage to a constant large voltage in the bridge.

Thus, the differential resistance R shows the resistance in the alternating current with a small amplitude at a certain voltage [3].

R at different temperatures, an anomaly was observed here, as in the static voltammetric characteristic.

4-5 V, the sign of the temperature coefficient of resistance changes. The corresponding temperature depends on the applied voltage and the thickness of the *n* semiconductor. The higher the voltage, the higher the inversion temperature.

As the thickness of the *n* semiconductor increases, the point of change of the sign of the temperature coefficient of resistance shifts to the lower temperature side, and the inversion occurs at a larger voltage.

In the electrical equivalent circuit of the selenium rectifier, the resistance connected in series with the

capacitance and resistance of the connecting layer is denoted by r . This resistance is the resistance of the selenium layer.

Experiments show that r approximately replaces the resistance of the quasi-neutral layer of selenium. As the thickness of the semiconductor p increases, the value of r increases in the elements. This value decreases as the percentage of halogen additives in selenium increases and the working area of the sample increases.

When no voltage is applied, the value of r for selenium elements is 60-100 ohm cm^2 [2]. The voltage dependence of r is reminiscent of the Voltan characteristic of the junction layer.

The difference is that in this case the layer is created next to the lining and acts in a straight direction.

Perhaps this layer is formed as a result of the difference in contact potentials between the metal and the semiconductor. The structural properties of the grown crystals were characterized by scanning electron microanalyzer and X-ray diffraction methods. Formation processes of various selenium crystal structures are discussed [6].

It can be seen from the figure that all the curves have a common course. A maximum is obtained at a certain value of the positive voltage. Two events play a major role in the decrease of r in the straight direction. First, as the voltage increases from 0.2 V, the thickness of the quasi-stationary layer of selenium increases.

Second, the composition of r includes the resistance of the transition layer between selenium and the lining layer.

It increases to the value of 0.2 V of the direct voltage, and decreases due to the effect of the magnetic field caused by its further growth.

Figure 2 shows the dependence of r on the applied voltage for three samples with an area of 11.45 cm^2 and *CdS* artificial layers.

Figure 2 . Variation of the series resistance in the equivalent circuit of the element selenium as a function of displacement (curves obtained from CdS layered samples)

From the opposite direction, as a result of the disappearance of the binding layer near the lining and the thinning of the selenium layer, r decreases.

temperature dependence of $CdSr$ for a layered sample is shown in figure

Figure 3 . Equivalent elements of selenium in different displacements temperature dependence of series resistances in the circuit

It can be seen that the resistance decreases in a straight line with temperature over negative and positive displacement voltages. These curves resemble the temperature dependence of the linear stress for the doped samples. Many chemical and physical properties of materials depend largely on the shape and size of the crystal. Here, single crystals of selenium with different morphologies and structures were created through a solvothermal crystallization process using four types of

ready-made solvents (CS₂, ethanol, benzene, and pyridine).

Conclusion

1. The rectification effect of selenium rectifiers is determined by the value of the change in the thickness of the binding layer in a changing electric field. Maximum shrinkage in the straight direction and expansion in the opposite direction are the main factors of straightening.

2. Selenium forms several allotropes that interconvert with temperature, depending somewhat on the rate of temperature change.

3. As a result, as the absolute value of the capacity drops, its temperature dependence becomes sharper. This shows that the capacitance is mainly due to the variation of layer thickness in *the pn* junction.

4. Due to the growth of the resistance of the selenium layer at low temperature, its capacity increases; since this capacitance is connected in series with the capacitance of the bonding layer, its increase reduces the capacitance of the element. However, as a result of the increase of the Debye radius at the boundary of the semiconductors, the reduction of the contact layer capacitance plays a key role in the reduction of the element's capacity.

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